

Psychotherapy, Insurgency And Insecurity In The North-Eastern Region Of Nigeria

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Abstract

The Boko Haram insurgency has lately introduced a terrorist dimension into the crime space in Nigeria. The trademarks of the Boko Haram are wanton destruction of lives and property with reckless abandon, through bombings, abduction and slaughtering of human beings like rams, especially in Northern Nigeria. This has created palpable fear and sense of insecurity in the polity. It is a fact that the development of any country in the world is dependent on many factors, which may fast-track or retards its growth, among which security is central. Security of lives and property plays a major role in the development of any country, as investors in any economy want to be assured of the safety of their investments. The Boko Haram attacks have led to the direct exposure of children to unimaginable violence; horrors, bombing, killings, hardship, kidnapping, diseases, and family displacement. The general objective of this study is to examine the psychotherapy, insurgency and insecurity in Nigeria. This study employs qualitative research method in which analytic approach was used to address the research questions raised. The phenomenon of insurgency in Nigeria which subsequently led to the mass population displacement in the country is no doubt unconnected to the fragile nature of state and state institutions. Theoretically, it is proven in this paper that fragile nature of Nigerian state which failed to carry out its constitutional responsibilities of providing security and welfare to citizens was largely responsible for insurgency. Special rehabilitation and trauma centres should be established, especially for women and children who have had horrible experiences during the insurgency period. Traumaexposed individuals should be given special psychological debriefing treatment to prevent and contain possible post-traumatic stress and disorder (PTSD). Porous border controls should be intensified with intelligence gathering technologies in order to halt weapons and track illegal border movements and obscured border to halt weapons and track illegal border movements and obscured border crossings through collaborative efforts of regional border security personnel.

Key word: *Psychotherapy, Insurgency and Insecurity.*

Introduction

A peaceful, stable and secure environment is considered to be one of the basic needs of every society (Huggins *et al* 2012). Security

in any society can be achieved in a tranquil situation devoid of threats to lives and property. Some of these threats are terrorism, political instability, environmental

degradation, economic meltdown, religious intolerance, to mention a few. Amongst these threats, domestic terrorism has currently drawn the attention of the world as developed and developing countries faced with threats of domestic terrorism (Peterside 2014: 283)

The major political phenomenon that has disturbed Nigeria unity and threatened its national security in recent time was insurgency. This scenario has not only hampered government efforts to provide security to its citizens as part of its constitutional responsibility but exposed the state's boundaries to more attack capable of frustrating state's defense against external aggression. Though insurgency and organized crime against constituted authority is a product of history as many societies has faced security challenges in recent times thanks to organized insurgency. For instance, Musa, Abba and Baba (2016), opined that every generation in human history has experience one form of rebellion. Modern society certainly has faced numerous challenges and insurgency is one such challenge and it has tremendous effects on society because it is an organized rebellion against constituted authority. Insurgency thus is not peculiar to developing nations as argued by Musa et al but became existential feature of every modern state. In Nigeria, where the insurgency was in rise, the country has witnessed displacement of large numbers of its citizens as a result of this menace.

The drastic increase has resulted in several studies on the effects of terrorism on the Nigerian population (e.g., Okoli & Philip, 2014; & Olaniyan, 2015). The Boko Haram attacks have led to the direct exposure of children to unimaginable violence; horrors, bombing, killings, hardship, kidnapping, diseases, and family displacement.

Daily exposure of children to Boko Haram violence, if not addressed may lead to internalization of violence, bitterness and psychological health problems which may impact the health of Nigerian children in the long run. Hayes and McAllister (2009) and Peredo (2015) have shown that terrorism is a way of producing psychological trauma and long term resentment, bitterness, and violence in children. When terrorism occurred, children develop fear for the future, and personal conception of safety and their security becomes compromised. Comer and Kendal (2007) identified direct exposure and indirect exposure to the ways which children may be exposed to terrorism. It was indirect exposure when children family were affected by death or displacement or when children watch the horror of terrorism through television or media directly experienced terrorism in or resides in the location where terrorism occurred. A direct exposure occurred when terrorism was conducted in the presence of the children.

The rapid increase in the intensity of insurgency carried out by Boko Haram has led to the exposure of approximately 2.5 million children in Nigeria to terrorism (UNICEF, 2016). These children live in fear of the unknown, are displaced, malnourished, suffer direct injury, and experience daily kidnappings, killings, and rapes. The childhood effect of being a direct victim of terrorist attacks could be devastating and long lasting with permanent psychological problem spanning from birth to adolescence and to the adulthood (Pine, Costello, & Masten, 2005). Extant studies on epidemiology established a direct link between children mental health problem and various levels of posttraumatic stress disorder with direct exposure to terrorism (Hussey, Chang & Kotch, 2006; Pynoos *et al.*, 1999, Steinberg & Avenevoli, 2000). A

similar position was expressed by the WHO (2006) when it found that at least 10% of the people who experienced highly dangerous events would have serious mental health problems. The WHO claimed that these dangerous circumstances will hinder the ability of the individuals to function effectively (Kessler & Üstün, 2004).

However, the association of terrorism with mental health is not consistent. Studies (e.g., North & Pfefferbaum, 2002) showed that the distress that children suffered during exposure to terrorism is considered “normative response” that may not necessarily be regarded as pathological responses. North and Pfefferbaum (2002) argued that many people experienced psychological problems than psychiatric illnesses; as such psychological problems should not be missed with psychiatric illnesses. Okasha and Elkholy (2012) echoed similar position when they argued that it is unknown if children who were directly or indirectly exposed to terrorist attacks inevitably experienced deteriorated mental health and if there are available or effective resilience and coping mechanism to the children. Such simple views are questionable in Nigeria. Most of the studies that predict association of terrorism with children traumas were longitudinal designs, with scientific research designs which imposed statistical data to analyses and predict the outcome (Kano, Wood, Siegel, & Bourque, 2016; Slone & Mann, 2016).

According to Adesote and Peter (2015), Internal Population Displacement (IPD) has become one of the human tragedies confronting the world today. In Nigeria for example, every citizen has recognized it as a critical and major problem which is largely blamed on flood, erosion and conflicts. Of these causes of internal population displacement, the conflict –

induced (which could be ethno-religious, inter-ethnic, intra and inter communal and political) appears to be more, and is therefore given prominence in this discourse. These induced conflicts have resulted in large wave of internal displacement of thousands of people. The deleterious consequences of this national security failure, thus is displacement of mass population. Statistically, it is submitted that the volume and spread of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) in Nigeria which is the function of insurgency was on increased; that about 1.4million displaced persons are been hosted across the country, for example, Akwa-Ibom (200,000); Cross-River (115,000); Ebonyi (80,000); Bauchi (45,000); Kebbi (50,000); Jigawa (200,000); Plateau (250,000); Taraba (250,000); Benue (480,000); Gombe (100,000); Edo (250,000); and Borno states (16,000). (Muhammed, 2012).

This statistics of internal displacement in Nigeria vividly shows that the incidence has constituted security challenges to both government and host communities. It is often said that security is the primary responsibility of any state without which the state sovereignty will be in question. The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria specifically states that “The security and welfare of the people shall be the primary concern of the government” (FRN, 1999). It is not an exaggeration to state that the constitutional responsibility of Nigerian government to provide security for her subjects has in one way or the other failed due to the inability of government to provide a secured and safe environment for lives and properties and even that of economic activities. The alarming rate of insecurity in Northern Nigeria has increased; the crime rate and terrorist attacks in different parts of the country leaving people in the north in an unpalatable situation by

rendering them homelessness. (Abdulrahman & Zuwaira, 2016). Though it is true to say that many factors accounted for the population displacement in Nigeria such as flood, famine, violence crisis and other emergency disasters. Internally Displaced Persons IDPs in Nigeria is no doubt the result of induced violence crisis in form of insurgency. These insurgencies which subsequently caused population displacement is generally believed to be result of constituted authority (government) negligence in providing social needs of citizens. This is clearly captured by Adesoji as thus; Marginalization and imbalance distribution or implementation of resources are the major factors that led to poverty in Nigeria which simplified the recruitment process of the group. Moreover, the failure of Nigerian leaders to establish economic policies that will improve the living standard of people and create employment opportunities among the youth has created a vacuum of unemployment, poverty and illiteracy among the youth, which resulted in various communal, ethnic, religious, and class conflicts that have now characterised the country and contributed to the emergence and Boko Haram (Adesoji, 2010). Of all the social menace in Nigeria that caused internal population displacement, Boko Haram insurgency was the most single social epidemic that caused contemporary national challenges of internally displaced persons IDPs.

The radicalism of this group of insurgents is the result of government failure to address the socio-economic needs of its citizenry as argued by Adesoji. The implication for these negative political phenomenon and security failure is already glaring. The IDPs phenomenon has not only caused more security challenges to constituted authority but to communities that

hosted displaced population. In reality, insecurity in any environment constitutes threat to lives and properties, hinders economic activities, and discourages local and foreign investors, and in turn, retards human and economic development of that nation. Nigeria is in a serious danger and looking at the position insecurity has put the giant country in Africa, a situation where over 350 teachers were killed and over 270 students were kidnapped and held captive in an unknown location for ever. (Abdulrahman & Zuwaira, 2016).

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria, as a country, is under internal security threats occasioned by acts of domestic terrorism which greatly affects the nations stability and well-being (Ogundiya, 2009:31). Prominent among these acts of domestic terrorism are ethno-religious fighting, violent and un-abated attacks in the oil-rich Niger-Delta, small arms proliferation, hostage-taking and kidnapping, bombing and wanton destruction of property (Ogundiya, 2009; pp31-32). Domestic terrorism, especially hostage taking and kidnapping negate security and where there is no security, anarchy strives and there is no development. There is an urgent need for the Federal Government of Nigeria to curb hostage-taking and kidnapping due to the consequent threat to national security. Any threat to the national security will definitely have far-reaching negative consequences on Nigeria's foreign image, the country as a whole and the world at large

Objectives of this Study

The general objective of this study is to examine the psychotherapy, insurgency and insecurity in Nigeria. However, the specific objectives of this are;

- i. To examine the root causes of insurgency and insecurity in Nigeria.
- ii. To identify the implications of insurgency and insecurity in Nigeria

Conceptual Clarifications

Psychotherapy is the use of psychological methods, particularly when based on regular personal interaction, to help a person change behavior and overcome problems in desired ways. Psychotherapy aims to improve an individual's well-being and mental health, to resolve or mitigate troublesome behaviors, beliefs, compulsions, thoughts, or emotions, and to improve relationships and social skills. Certain psychotherapies are considered evidence-based for treating some diagnosed mental disorders. Others have been criticized as pseudoscience.

There are over a thousand different psychotherapy techniques, some being minor variations, while others are based on very different conceptions of psychology, ethics (how to live), or techniques. Most involve one-to-one sessions, between client and therapist, but some are conducted with groups,^[1] including families.

Psychotherapists may be mental health professionals such as psychiatrists, psychologists, clinical social workers, marriage and family therapists, or professional counselors. Psychotherapists may also come from a variety of other backgrounds, and depending on the jurisdiction may be legally regulated, voluntarily regulated or unregulated (and the term itself may be protected or not).

Hundreds of thousands of people have also been psychologically traumatised by horrific things they see during the insurgency period. Most of them need to be psychologically rehabilitated in order to re-integrate them back into their societies. Women and children have had their

husbands, fathers and brothers slain or hacked to death in their presence and their properties and villages torched to ashes. Boko Haram has displaced millions of persons, including a substantial number of children and more than \$67m is needed to rehabilitate the displaced and psychologically traumatised persons on the North Eastern part of Nigeria, especially children whose situation is one of the worst in the world (Red Cross, May, 2015). Every child needs education, physical and emotional support so as to grow up as a responsible adult, but problems for children usually come up from lack of, poor or abusive family, physical and emotional disabilities (White & White, 1980:98).

Without proper (in some cases, clinical) rehabilitation of the insurgency victims, many will never come back to normal life and others, especially children, are bound to wicker, heartless and brutal in the remaining parts of their lives for what they had seen and undergone under the insurgency. In addition, many of those refugees, especially children have lost both parents and societal care to which Stewart (1977: 76) has noted that "... the child's psychological development is profound and significantly influenced by the kind of care he or she receives". For that, such children are also likely to lack social intelligence as the ability to respect other perspectives, avoid hurting others unintentionally, making friends (Brophy, 1977: 359). In the same vein, Zastraw & Ashman (2010: p.96) have noted that 'psychological factors act together with biological and social conditions which then determine and influence individual's actions, reactions, condition and behavior.

Boko Haram insurgency has resulted in large number orphaned children and widows. 60% of all the persons in the internally displaced camps established as a

result of Boko Haram insurgency are women and children. Likewise, 60% of all the children in these camps are orphans and such children face socio-psychological, medical, economic and environmental challenges as a result. Zastraw & Ashman (2010: p.204) have noted that neglected children suffer from or are victims of physical and mental health care (unattended), educationally neglected, without proper and normal life supervision, face housing hazards, lack proper household and basic personal and sanitation, face social and attachment difficulties, lack basic nutrition, encounter cognitive and academic deficits and also have emotional and behavioural problems. One other potential threat of the post Boko Haram era is the presence of neglected children all over the affected areas and by extension, other places. This is because there are a large number of orphans all over, those others are abused in one form or the other and in widespread poverty and children and women are worst in affected areas. As a result of the insurgency, there are more than 5, 000 orphans in the North-Eastern region alone (National Emergency Management Agency, NEMA, December, 2015). These children/orphans are, if not urgently attended to will grow up uneducated, unprepared for life challenges, unemployed, and criminals as well as counterproductive to the Nigerian state and society (see also Badiora, 2017).

Insurgency: This is often seen as an action by organize groups with the instrument of violence with aim of frustrating constituted authority to further achieve their social, economic and political motives. From the perspective of Musa *et al* (2016) insurgency or rebellion is a movement aimed at replacement or violent attempt to take control of legally existing constituted

government or society through the use of armed conflict or subversion. The Advanced English Dictionary defined insurgency as an organized rebellion aimed at overthrowing a constituted government through the use of subversion and arm conflict. It is indeed a rebellion against authority. There are two distinguish features that characterized insurgency, these are use of violence and intention to change the government action or to overthrow the sitting government.

According to Powell and Abraham (2006), Insurgency refers to a violent move by a person or group of persons to resist or oppose the enforcement of law or running of government or revolt against constituted authority of the state or of taking part in insurrection. The United States Department of Defense (DOD) defines it as this: "An organized movement aimed at the overthrow of a constituted government through use of subversion and armed conflict". According to Kilcullen, "Insurgency is a struggle to control a contested political space, between a state (or a group of states or occupying powers), and one or more popularly based, non-state challengers". He further draws a line between classical and contemporary insurgencies indicating that the latter seek to replace the existing order, while the former sometimes strive for the expulsion of foreign invaders from their territory or seek to fill an existing power vacuum (Kilcullen, 2006). The French expert on war Bernard said that "revolutionary warfare" (guerrilla warfare plus political action) might be a more accurate term to describe small wars such as insurgencies. (Bernard, 1965). This definition is a true reflection of nature of insurgencies in Nigeria where Boko Haram insurgents hide in bushes in form of Guerrilla and unleash violence on the populace from their hide out. It is on this note that Robert submitted that Insurgencies differ in their use of tactics and methods. He

also identified four essential elements that are identifiable with insurgency these are;

1. Cell-networks that maintain secrecy.
2. Terrorism used to foster insecurity among the population and drive them to the insurgents for protection
3. Attacks against the government (Robert, 2004)

The principal aim of insurgency therefore is to create tension with the instrument of violence capable of frustrating the constituted authorities to yield to their interior demands. These demands could be economic in nature and sometime could be political with sole aim of changing entire political structure or eliminating a particular regime.

Insecurity: The concept of insecurity connotes different meanings such as: absence of safety; danger; hazard; uncertainty; lack of protection, and lack of safety. According to Beland (2005) insecurity is a state of fear or anxiety due to absence or lack of protection. Achumba *et al* (2013) defines insecurity from two perspectives. Firstly, insecurity is the state of being open or subject to danger or threat of danger, where danger is the condition of being susceptible to harm or injury. Secondly insecurity is the state of being exposed to risk or anxiety, where anxiety is a vague unpleasant emotion that is experienced in anticipation of some misfortune. These definitions of Journal of Sustainable Development Studies security underscore a major point that those affected by insecurity are not only uncertain or unaware of what would happen but they are also vulnerable to the threats and dangers when they occur. In the context of this paper insecurity is defined as a breach of peace and security, whether historical, religious, ethno-regional, civil, social, economic, and

political that contributes to recurring conflicts, and leads to wanton destruction of lives and property.

Internally Displaced Persons IDPs:

Internally displaced persons often shorten as IDPs are people who flee their home as a result of violence conflict but look for a temporary settlement within the boarder of their country. IDP therefore is distinguishable from refugees which some people use indiscriminately. The distinguishing feature between IDPs and refugees is that IDPs are displaced from their home and settle within their country's boarder, the refugees are displaced population that flee beyond the boarder of their country and are protected by international law. The United Nations Guiding Principles on the protection and assistance of Internally Displaced Persons IDPs has offered elaborate definition of IDPs as;

Internally displaced people are people or groups of people who have been forced or obliged to flee or to leave their homes or places of habitual residence, in particular as a result of or in order to avoid the effects of armed conflict, situations of generalized violence, violations of human rights or natural or human-made disasters, and who have not crossed an internationally recognized state border (UNGP, 1998).

This definition is all encompasses and vividly shows that people may flee their home when there is imminent attack to a safer place to avoid loss of lives and destruction of moveable properties. In his own contribution to the meaning of IDPs, Ladan using international law approach described IDPs as Displaced persons under international law are persons or groups of persons who have been forced or obligated to flee or to have cause to leave their homes or place of habitual residence in particular,

due to or in order to stave off the effect of armed conflict, violations of human rights, situations of generalized violence, natural or man-made disasters, to another place considered relatively safe either within their own national borders (as internally displaced persons) or travel across an internationally recognized state border (as refugees) (Ladan, 2006). Ladan's definition buttresses on the UN guiding principles definition by developing a dichotomy between IDPs and refugees. Displacement of persons could be cause by many factors. Although internally displaced persons IDPs are often defined as those uprooted by conflict, human rights violations and natural or human-made disasters, Robinson (2003) expanded the scope to also include those displaced by development projects. Most times, the focus of sympathetic attention and international aid centre round those displaced by disaster than for victims of development.

Theoretical Framework

The fundamental element of any research objective is to theorize its problem with aim of providing workable solution to the problem identified. Theory thus is the basic tool of analysis. For the purpose of this work, failed state theory is employed to unravel the causes and implication of insurgency and IDPs in Nigeria. Central to this theory is that state which has the constitutional responsibilities of protecting and providing welfare to its citizens failed to do so because of weak institutions and bad leadership. UK Department for the Development (United Kingdom, 2005) sees failed state from the humanitarian point of view, where the government cannot or will not deliver core functions to the majority of its people including the poor. He further sees a failed state as the insecurity of the ruling elites which leads to the victimization of some or all of nations citizens as

experienced by the Taliban's in Afghanistan.

The failed state theory stresses the fundamental failure of a state to perform functions necessary to meet citizen's basic needs and expectations. It also shows the incapability of government in assuring basic security, maintaining rule of law and justice, or providing basic services and economic opportunities for their citizens (Imasuen, 2015). The centrality of failed state theory posits weak and ineffective central government with little practical control over much of its territory; non-provision of public services widespread corruption and criminality; refugees and involuntary movement of populations (Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, 2008).

Rotberg (2003) notes that in a failed state, there is a tendency for increased criminal violence which further weakens the states' authority. He further notes that failed states are usually associated with tensed, deeply conflicted and dangerous warring factions which most times leads to breakdown of law and order, increased humanitarian disaster, which concerns not only the people directly affected, but also others in the country as well as people in neighbouring states. Torres and Anderson (2004) argue that conflicts, humanitarian crises, human right violations, constitute to the global and local impact of failed states. Collier *et al.* (2003) identify three ripple effects that emerge from armed conflict: they are the internal effects (as a result of the burdens of internally displaced persons), the regional effects (as a result of the burden of refugees' influx) and the global effect (as a result of foreign interventionists). According to him, these three ripple effects generate unique challenges. While the internal effects constitutes problem of food

insecurity, loss of means of livelihood, rise in displacement of people, the regional effect constitute spread of contagious diseases across borders from the inflow of refugees and the global effect constitute the growth in narcotics trade across borders sponsored by foreign non state actors.

Boko Haram insurgency, political violence, corruption, nepotism, tribalism, indiscipline, abduction and kidnappings, armed robbery, murder and extortion, bombings of places of worship and innocent Nigerians are all the indicators of a failing state. Nigerian ship can thus be said to be heading for rock as the country was characterized with all the above features of a failed state.

To apply this theory to this study, with the rebirth of democratic rule in Nigeria in 1999, many Nigerians were hopeful that restoration of civilian government will put an end to poverty, unemployment, inequality, social vices such as robbery, theft and other ills of development. To the surprised of most Nigerians, this hope has turned to frustration as government failed to address these development challenges. The government inability to perform its constitutional functions including security of lives and properties therefore informed people to be rebellion and take up arms against same government chiefly to protest their socio-economic challenges. This theory is also related to this study as insurgents groups in Nigeria recruited from vulnerable citizens who suffered from poverty, unemployment, inequality, and untold hardship. The activities of these insurgents groups which caused citizens to be internally displaced are the function of state negligence towards its primary responsibilities.

Also, the displacement of mass population facilitated the heinous act of group like Boko Haram who recruits the

children of displaced population. This is the result of lackadaisical attitude by government towards the plight of IDPs in their various camps in Nigeria.

Insurgency in Nigeria: A Brief Historical Account

A critical analysis of checkered Nigeria political history would reveal that country was ransacked with series of crisis and insurgency which has disturbed the unity of the country. Perhaps, the various crises that engulfed the country were displayed base on national consciousness and dignity of ethnic considerations. It is on this note that Allswell (2014) pointed out that Previous insurgencies in Nigeria have varied in their scope, sophistication and intensity.

There have been at least six instances. These are; Nigerian civil war, Declaration of Niger Delta Republic, Movement for the actualisation of the sovereign state of Biafra, Movement for the emancipation of the Niger Delta and related insurgencies, Oodua People's Congress, Northern Arewa groups, Jama'atu Ahlil Sunna Lidawati wal Jihad (BokoHaram) (Allswell, 2014). Each of these insurgent groups carried out their insurgencies in different dimensions purposely to achieve their socio-political and economic motives.

There were other minor insurgencies in Nigeria ranging from ethnic to religions violence that claim lives and destruction of properties. Adesote and Peters (2015) for instance gave historical account of some violence crisis in Nigeria since independence in 1960. According to him, Nigeria had witnessed series of violence prior to her political independence in 1960. This violence happened as a result of the introduction of various policies of the British administration, like taxation. Notable examples of such violence or uprising were the 1929 Aba women riot in the East and the

1916 Iseyin-Okeho uprising in the West. The first major ethnic violent that occurred in the post-colonial period took place in the Western Region and was between Chief Obafemi Awolowo and Chief Ladoke Akintola in 1962. The rift between them led to a series of crises and clashes which invariably led to the declaration of a State of Emergency (Falola, et al, 1990). The Northern region was the second region that experienced another ethnic violent. This took place in Kaduna, the seat of Government and headquarters of the region. The first major crisis to erupt in Kaduna was as a result of the assassination of Sir Ahmadu Bello, the Sarduna of Sokoto in a bloody coup d'état of January 15, 1966 led by Kaduna Nzeogwu, an Igbo ethnic stock. However, the most murderous group in the history of Nigerian political violence emerged in 2000s. This group known popularly as Boko Haram embarked on coordinated insurgencies by destroying villages, bombing religious institutions, government institution and most wickedly suicide bombing where thousands of people are often killed and injured.

Rationale or Causes of Insurgency in Nigeria

Insecurity in the Northern Nigeria is a function of government failure or could be linked to governmental failure. This is true due to the inability of government to deliver public service and provide for basic needs of the masses. The lack of basic necessities by the people of Northern Nigeria has created a pool of frustrated people who are ignited easily by any event to be violent (Igbuzor, 2011). The fundamental and constitutional function of any state is security and provision of welfare package to its citizens. Any state that failed to provide these basic functions of a state has derailed from its constitutional responsibilities and the result

will be hostilities from citizen which may transform to violence crisis. The high level of negligence on the part of Nigerian government especially in Northern region as argued by Igbuzor above is responsible for insurgency in the region. An income disparity was also identified as the motivating factor that induced insurgency in Nigeria. For instance, Abdulrahman and Zuwaira (2016), averred that disparities in the way of life of the people is one major factor responsible for the insecurity in the Northern Nigeria which has created a negative perception about the region. The problem of inequality and unfairness on the side of their leaders has raised the anger of a large number of people in that region. Poverty as is often argued is the bane of all society and constitutes a serious obstacle to societal development. This is why Allswell (2014), opined that among several other ills, poverty breeds anger, hatred, envy and conflict. This is a clear justification that any poverty driven or stricken society could be characterized by insurgency as a manifestation of people's destituteness and hopelessness. Mailafia has elaborately linked poverty and rate of insurgency in Northern Nigeria. According to him; the prevalence of poverty makes it easier for extremist groups to mobilise disenchanted mobs in pursuit of their own political goals. In Northern Nigeria, where over 70 per cent of the population lives under the internationally-defined poverty line, it is easy to see how any demagogue or religious extremist can mobilize the poor and destitute as instruments for his own political goals. There is the added factor of youth unemployment, especially within the growing stratum of university graduates. When people are pushed to the lowest levels of desperation and hopelessness, they can fall easy prey to religious demagogues who offer them a sense of belonging. (Mailafia,

2012). Any rebellion groups thus can take over the role of a state by giving the government's neglected or vulnerable citizens sense of belonging and in turn receive loyalty from these desperate people and subsequently use them as an insurgents against the same constituted authority. Similarly, Ojolo has succinctly opined that group grievances and other social vices ignited the insurgencies in the country. To him; Individuals and groups grievances such as poverty, unemployment, illiteracy, discrimination, and economic marginalization, can be used as mobilizing instruments by sinister group to get support and recruit for terrorist violence. The predominantly Muslim northern Nigeria provide the group a steady stream for recruitment, the deprived youths and Almajiris are willing to join any movement for them to find an alternative to the current economic and political inequalities that existed in the country; believing that the sect version of radical Salafism to be the answer to their problems. (Ojolo, 2013). Ojolo's position is true as economic realities is the prime motivator or driver of insurgency especially in Northern Nigeria where economic disadvantaged people can be financially induced and recruit them as potential insurgents. Senator Shehu Sani identified thirteen causative factors that ignited insurgency in Nigeria. These factors are; manipulation of religion, disconnect between government and the governed, prevalence of social and economic injustices, global terror epidemic – terror contagion, collapse of public education, massive unemployment, proliferation of arms and unguarded borders, under-development of the North by previous administrations, Human right abuses and extra-judicial killings, economic collapse of the North, capitalism, lack of unity and ethnic crisis in the North and distortion of

religious realities (Sani, 2015). The consequences of these social malaises as identified by Sani are no doubt ignition of violent conflicts that could cause population displacement. In addition, International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD 2007) said “despite Nigeria’s plentiful resources and oil wealth, poverty is widespread to the extent that the country is ranked one of the 20 poorest countries in the world”. Indeed over 70 percent of the population is classified as poor, with 35 percent living in absolute poverty. Poverty is what is seen by many observers and analysts as the cause of most ethno religious crisis in Northern Nigeria which Boko Haram insurgency included.

According to Blanchard (2011: 10): Understanding Boko Haram’s appeal among some citizen in Nigeria’s far north requires an examination of underlying development challenges facing northern Nigeria, where high rates of poverty and unemployment are exacerbated by extreme population growth and low level of literacy. These factors combined with weak governance, rampant corruption and inadequate public service delivery, has contributed to widespread disaffection that some suggest may facilitate Boko Haram recruitment (Salisu & Mohammed, 2015). This justifies that government inability to address social menace like poverty and unemployment is directly linked to the mass rise of insurgents groups which claims many lives and most worriedly disturbed the unity of the country.

Similarly, religious and ideological traits could also be motivating factor that induced insurgency in Nigeria. According to Allswll (2014), competitions between religious and ideological forces as manifest elsewhere in the Nigerian state. Apart from Christianity and Islam, numerous other religions are practised in Nigeria, and these,

as would be expected, permeate the prevailing ideological types which compete in the country with various degrees of favour and levels of followership. Conflict is bound to arise in the ensuing competition between religious and ideological types and their adherents. Thus, for example, in a community where the elders adhere to traditions and religious practices of the ancestors, any deviation by the youth from the norms prescribed by the community is likely to be a cause of conflict. (Allswell, 2014). The ideological trait of Boko Haram insurgents in Nigeria could attest to this fact as the group did not only believe in Islamizing the entire region but massive killing of individuals who do not yield to their believe.

Insurgency and Insecurity in Nigeria: The Implications

Violence has reached unprecedented levels and hundreds have been killed with much more wounded or displaced from their homes on account of their ethnic or religious identification. Schooling for children has been disrupted and interrupted; businesses have lost billions of naira and property worth much more destroyed (Obasanjo, 2004). The deleterious consequences of insurgency on the economy and well-being of a state cannot be underestimated. The insurgencies has crippled the economic activities of Nigeria and destroyed educational institutions. The billions of Naira lost to insurgency in Nigeria as espoused by Obasanjo above could have been channel to development of major economy sectors such as construction of roads, rehabilitation of educational institutions, improvement in medical cares and provision of general services to the entire population. The most disastrous implication of insurgency on the political space referred to as Nigeria is Social

dislocation and displacement. It was obvious that in 2014, over 140,000 people were displaced from their homes, villages, communities and states in the north. In 2015, over 70,000 Nigerians were reported to have fled the country to other neighboring countries like Cameroon, Niger, Benin Republic, Chad, etc. It is also evidence that within Nigeria, there are about 1000 IDPs camps across the 36 states of the federation and the Federal Capital Territory with most of the IDPs from the north. (Abdulrahman & Zuwaira, 2016). According to the Office for Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), almost the entire population of IDPs in Borno, estimated to have been almost a million by the third Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) produced by the International Organization for Migration (IOM) and the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) is now in Maiduguri. The State camps have more than 15,000 IDPs and more continue to arrive every week (OCHA, 2015). IDPs also suffered many casualties such as shortage of foods, health facilities and lack of shelter during rainy seasons. For instance OCHA submitted that the number of IDPs has continued to climb, the amount of resources devoted to the camps such as food and shelter have remained the same. People in each camp are grouped according to their LGAs. Besides, SEMA attempts to distribute the food rations, based on the buying power of the respective LGAs' budgets. Lack of an adequate number of latrines to keep up with the growing numbers of people in camps and the rains have heightened the risk of possible outbreaks of waterborne diseases. In Dalori, an aid worker said 80 latrines were being shared by more than 15,000 residents (OCHA, 2015).

Between 2013 and 2014, more than 5000 people have been killed in Boko Haram violence. United Nations and Nigerian officials reported that more than six million Nigerians have been affected, and more 300,000 have been displaced. And at least 2000 have been killed in the first half 2014 (Blanchard 2014). Consequently, the threats posed by the group recently undermined the existence of Nigeria as one territory. The insurgency also has negative implication on social tension and new patterns of settlements. Muslims moving to Muslim dominated areas while Christians on the other hand migrating to Christian dominated areas. A good example is the situation in Jos North/South of Plateau states (Abdulrahman & Zuwaira, 2016). This phenomenon will no doubt reinforced ethnic identity and promote ethnic, religious and sectional consciousness as opposed to national unity irrespective of our religions believed. Insurgency has also increased cost of governance, the situation of insecurity in Nigeria especially in the North-East has forced the government of Nigeria to deploy high volume of the nation's resources to fight Boko Haram insurgency in that part of the country with little success been recorded. For instance, in 2014 National Budget, over one trillion naira was voted for security. The relocation of the Defence Command Centre from Abuja to Maiduguri by President Muhammadu Buhari on the 29th May, 2015 is a typical example of how insecurity has forced the federal government of Nigeria into extra budgetary spending (Abdulrahman & Zuwaira, 2016).

Most of the families in the affected areas of Borno, Adamawa and Yobe have lost their homes and resettled in IDP (Internally displaced persons) camps. The composition and settlement in the camp does not provide the conducive environment

to enforce family values. Some of them have lost their family members while thousands of children are in the camps without parents or kinsmen. Certainly they are experiencing trauma in an alien environment coupled with the fact that they don't have the opportunity of schooling. The physical and psychological wounds of the insurgency will perhaps be indelible on these children (Musa *et al*, 2016). Butressing this view, Abdulrahman and Zuwaira (2016) averred that disruption of family and communal life essentially characterized the IDPs camps. This is one of the most painful effects of insecurity in the northern Nigeria. Since the insurgency started unleashing their activities, maiming, killing and burning of houses in that part of the country, a lot of people have lost their loved ones and others were forced to separate from each other. This invariably bestowed hardship on the face of many while others are still undergoing emotional and psychological trauma resulting from the act of insurgency in the north. During the violent conflicts or natural disaster, which forced these Internally Displaced Persons to leave, most houses and properties were destroyed, looted or burnt down. Most IDPs in Nigeria flee to neighbouring countries that are safe usually taking refuge in temporary shelter such as schools, public building and places of worship among others. Despite the efforts of the Nigerians, having been deprived of their homes and sometimes, their lives and livelihoods, government, faith based organizations and other NGOs to address some of the basic needs of these IDPs, their vulnerability tends to be increased by barriers to accessing healthcare services, education, employment, economic activities and information for participation in the decision making affecting their lives. Hence, the government spending and responsibilities equally increased.

Dehumanization of men, women and children especially in areas where rape, child abuse and neglect are used as instrument of war (Abdulrahman & Zuwaira, 2016). At this stage it is difficult to quantify the number of life, properties and settlements destroyed as a result of the insurgency. Household, market structures, worship place and government establishments (schools, hospitals, council secretariat) in Bama, Gwoza and Baga towns were almost completely burnt down. According to the International Organization for Migration (IMO), over 2.1 million have been internally displaced in the north east. In addition, estimates put the number killed at some 15,000 people though obviously it is much higher than this number Musa et'al (2016). In fact the implications of insurgency which caused mass population displacement cannot be overemphasized. The scenario has jeopardized the nation's economy, promote insecurity, destroyed educational system and fuel disunity among disparate ethnic groups that composed Nigeria and among the religions circle.

Method

This study employs qualitative research method in which analytic approach was used to address the research questions raised. A qualitative analytic method refers to identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns (themes) within the data collected for the purpose of the study (Braun and Clarke, 2006). For the purpose of this study, the researcher relied basically on secondary sources of data which includes textbooks, internet source and news concerning the issues under the study. The researcher used analytic and comparative approach to analyze the data collected.

Result

The phenomenon of insurgency in Nigeria which subsequently led to the mass

population displacement in the country is no doubt unconnected to the fragile nature of state and state institutions. Historically, it argues in this paper that many insurgents groups has emerged in Nigeria with different magnitude. However, the most murderous group in recent times is religion extremist popularly known as Boko Haram which claimed my lives and rendered thousands homeless. Theoretically, it is proven in this paper that fragile nature of Nigerian state which failed to carry out its constitutional responsibilities of providing security and welfare to citizens was largely responsible for insurgency. Insurgency therefore could be seen from wider perspective as a function of state negligence towards its citizens. The implication for this insurgency is multi-dimensional; the state become more insecure as the activities of insurgents groups make borders to be porous through which where weapon flows to the country. Most disastrously, the insurgents groups have caused people to flee their homes because of attack or fear of imminent attack thereby making citizens to become internally displaced within their own country. These displaced populations are neglected by constituted authority which facilitated their recruitment into insurgents groups. The implication for this therefore is more insecurity and collapse of the country's economy.

Discussion and Recommendation

The rises in insurgency and insecurity in Nigeria and phenomenon of Internally Displaced Persons IDPs has endangered the country's political economy which must be tackle if the country need to prosper. It is based on this that this work recommends the followings; Special rehabilitation and trauma centres should be established, especially for women and children who have had horrible experiences during the

insurgency period. Trauma exposed individuals should be given special psychological debriefing treatment to prevent and contain possible post-traumatic stress and disorder (PTSD).

The socio-economic conditions of citizens should be re-addressed by government. This is constitutional responsibility of government which if failed to carry-out may lead to social menace such as poverty, unemployment and inequality. These phenomena are said to be responsible for violence conflict in the country. Though conflict is inevitable in every society, Nigeria needs to strengthen its national security to avert violence conflict that would cause mass population displacement. The strengthening of security will also tremendously helps in protecting the borders from external aggressions. Institutional mechanism in Nigeria needs to be look into especially in the areas of addressing the plight of IDPs. Specific institution should be established with the principal responsibility of managing and assisting IDPs in the country.

Porous border controls should be intensified with intelligence gathering technologies in order to halt weapons and track illegal border movements and obscured border to crossings through collaborative efforts of regional border security personnel.

There should be prevention and special care by the authorities concerned and the general public for those affected by the insurgency, which forced them into the migration, unemployment, poverty and social degradation of life and urgently require sufficient housing, employment, income and children and parents keeping.

All the able bodied who helped the military in the fight against the insurgents such as the Civilian JTF should be integrated into the Nigerian Armed Forces

in order to contain their militarized spirits, intelligence and training.

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